

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The influence of work culture and leadership style on employee job satisfaction with work discipline as an intervening variable PT Hutama Karya Infrastruktur Jakarta

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Abstract

This study discusses how the influence of work culture and leadership style on employee job satisfaction with work discipline as an intervening variable of PT Hutama Karya Infrastruktur Jakarta. This research uses quantitative methods, with a population of 168 employees at PT HKI Jakarta. The sampling technique is a purposive sampling technique using the slovin formula, which is 113 respondents. The analytical test tool used is Smart PLS with SEM (Structural Equation Modeling) analysis method. The results of this study show that directly work discipline and leadership style have no effect on job satisfaction, organizational culture does not affect work discipline, organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, and leadership style has a positive and significant effect on work discipline. The results of the indirect test showed that organizational culture variables and leadership style did not have a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction through work discipline as an intervening variable.

Keywords: Work Culture; Leadership Style; Work Discipline; Job Satisfaction

1 Introduction

Employees are company assets that must be properly maintained, with the expectation that these assets provide commensurate return. The decline in company productivity is caused by employees who experience demotivation. Demotivation is a feeling in which we feel tired, lose enthusiasm, even give up on doing something or work. Many factors cause demotivation of workers, one of which is the lack of job satisfaction. Companies must recognize the factors that are able to generate job satisfaction for employees so that the company will continue to progress and develop and then carry out what the company should do to achieve job satisfaction.

Locke A., an American psychologist, stated that job satisfaction is a positive emotional state resulting from one's work experience. [1] Job Satisfaction is an employee attitude towards work related to work situations, cooperation between employees, benefits received at work, and matters concerning physical and psychological factors. Job satisfaction is the mood felt by employees at work because they get fulfillment of needs in the form of rewards (salaries and incentives), opportunities for career advancement, and colleagues who support in the process of completing work. But in reality there are still many employees who are not satisfied with the results of the work that has been achieved, ranging from the work given from superiors to achieve the work targets demanded by the company, the absence of promotion so that employees feel that the work to be done does not affect the results of work

There are several factors that affect job satisfaction, one of which is work culture. Work culture is a process of teaching certain knowledge and skills and attitudes so that employees are more skilled and able to carry out responsibilities better, in accordance with [2]. According to [3] that "work culture is the process of teaching the skills needed by employees to do their jobs". Corporate culture can have a meaningful impact on long-term economic performance. Work culture refers to the values, norms, beliefs, attitudes, and behaviors that exist in an organization. If an employee's

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personal values align with those espoused by the organization, they are more likely to feel satisfied with their work. When individual and organizational values match each other, it creates feelings of connectedness, identification, and pride that can increase job satisfaction

Another factor that also has a role in efforts to increase employee job satisfaction is Leadership Style. According to House in [4], said that: Leadership is the ability of individuals to influence, motivate, and make others able to contribute to the effectiveness and success of the organization. The leader's ability to influence others will provide motivation for employees to do something to achieve the desired goal. Leadership style can affect employee satisfaction. Effective leadership can create a positive work environment, motivate employees, and increase their satisfaction in their jobs. Conversely, ineffective leadership can lead to dissatisfaction, tension, and decreased motivation among employees. The way a leader influences the behavior of subordinates aims to encourage work passion, job satisfaction and high employee productivity, in order to achieve maximum organizational goals.

Another factor used to look at employee job satisfaction is work discipline. Work discipline is a mental attitude that is reflected in the actions or behavior of a person, a community group in the form of *obedience* to rules, norms that apply in society. [5] revealed that good discipline reflects the magnitude of a person's sense of responsibility towards the tasks given to him. This encourages morale, and the realization of the company's goals so that its subordinates have good discipline.

A work culture that supports and promotes values such as punctuality, discipline, and responsibility can increase an employee's level of work discipline. Employees tend to internalize and apply those values in the performance of their duties, which in turn can affect their job satisfaction. Similarly, a leadership style that is clear, fair, and provides support can encourage employees to be more disciplined in carrying out their duties. Conversely, an authoritarian or less supportive leadership style can reduce employees' motivation to be disciplined in their work. Thus, employees who have a high level of work discipline tend to have better performance and achieve targets consistently. This can provide a greater feeling of accomplishment and satisfaction with the work done. Conversely, lack of work discipline can lead to stress and dissatisfaction as tasks may not be fulfilled properly.

PT Hutama Karya Infrastruktur (HKI) is one of the subsidiaries of state-owned PT Hutama Karya (Persero) (HK) in the field of construction services business. Established in 2015, HKI is a *spin off* of HK's Road & Bridge Division which has been active since 1961. PT HKI is one of the 'largest construction companies in Indonesia that has a mission to develop strong and innovative human resources in order to increase company value' of course must measure the level of employee satisfaction in order to produce better employee productivity.

1.1. Work Culture

In the big Indonesian dictionary, culture is defined as: thoughts, customs, something that has developed, something that becomes a habit that is difficult to change. In everyday use, people usually synonymize the notion of culture with tradition. In this case, tradition is defined as the general ideas, attitudes and habits of the community that appear from the daily behavior that becomes the habit of the group in the community. In Robbins' opinion in [6], work culture is values that become habits and start from customs, religion, norms and rules that become beliefs in work actors or organizations.

Work culture is a process of teaching certain knowledge and skills and attitudes so that employees are more skilled and able to carry out responsibilities better, in accordance with [2]. According to [3], that "work culture is the process of teaching the skills needed by employees to do their jobs". Furthermore, the notion of work culture is simply defined by (Wahjono & Mondy (2015), as "a learning process designed to change the ability of employees to do their work".

The indicators in work culture according to [7] in [6] are: 1) Innovation and risk-taking, 2) Attention to details, 3) Results orientation, 4) Human orientation, 5) Team orientation, 6) Aggressiveness, 7) Stability

1.2. Leadership Style

Fiedler defined leadership by notions of a person who is in a group as a taskmaster or as an influence and coordinates the activities of the relevant group, as well as being the first person in charge. Davis defines leadership as the ability to persuade others to achieve a predetermined goal enthusiastically. Thus, leadership is the ability or ability of a person to persuade others to be willing to work hard in achieving organizational goals that have been set.

According to [8] leadership style is a trait, habit, temperament, disposition, and personality that distinguishes a leader in interacting with others. According to House in [4], said that: Leadership is the ability of individuals to influence,

motivate, and make others able to contribute to the effectiveness and success of the organization. So from House's opinion, it can be said that leadership is a way of influencing and motivating others so that these people want to contribute with good performance to the success of the organization.

According to [9] in [10] Leadership Style is a behavioral norm used by a person when the person tries to influence the behavior of others. Meanwhile, according to [11] in [10], leadership style is the ability to raise the spirit of others to be willing and have total responsibility for efforts to achieve or exceed organizational goals.

According to [8] in [12] a person's leadership style can be seen and assessed from several indicators as follows:

1. Decision-Making Ability
2. Motivating Ability
3. Communication Skills
4. Ability to control subordinates
5. Responsibility
6. Emotional Control Ability

1.3. Work Discipline

According to Terry as quoted by [13] suggests that discipline is a driving tool for employees. In order for every job to run smoothly, it must be tried so that there is good discipline.

This was then emphasized by [5] Good discipline reflects the magnitude of a person's sense of responsibility for the tasks given to him. This encourages morale, and the realization of the company's goals so that its subordinates have good discipline. A manager is said to be effective in his leadership if his subordinates are well disciplined.

Work Discipline as referred to is an attitude of respect, respect, obedience, and compliance with material guidelines, both compiled and unwritten and can do so and does not try not to be sanctioned in the event that he abuses his obligations and experts. given to him.

According to [5] basically many indicators affect the level of discipline of an employee including:

1. Goals and abilities
2. Leadership examples
3. Remuneration
4. Justice
5. Inherent supervision
6. Penalties
7. Assertiveness
8. Humanitarian relations

1.4. Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is a positive attitude of the workforce including feelings and behaviors towards their work through the assessment of one of the jobs as a sense of appreciation in achieving one of the important values of work [14]. According to [1] Job Satisfaction is an employee attitude towards work related to work situations, cooperation between employees, benefits received at work, and matters concerning physical and psychological factors.

According to [15], job satisfaction is "a general attitude toward a person's job that shows a difference between the amount of reward a worker receives and the amount they believe they should receive". According to [16], everyone who works expects to get satisfaction from where they work. Job Satisfaction will affect the productivity that managers expect. According to [17], employee job satisfaction is one of the most important elements in organizations.

According to [14], job satisfaction indicators are as follows:

- Work
- Wages
- Promotion
- Supervisor

- Co workers

2 Material and methods

2.1. Research Approach

This study is intended to determine how the influence of work culture, leadership style, and work discipline on employee satisfaction, so this study is categorized as explanatory research, which is research that aims to explain the causal relationship between variables through hypothesis testing. This study used quantitative methods.

2.2. Population and Sample

[18] explained that population is a generalized area consisting of objects or subjects that have certain quantities and characteristics determined by researchers to be studied and then drawn conclusions. The research population to be used in the study is all employees at PT HKI Jakarta totaling 168 people. The definition of sample according to [18] is as part of the number and characteristics possessed by a population. The sampling technique used in this study is a purposive sampling technique using the slovin formula. So the number of samples in this study was 113 respondents.

2.3. Data Analysis Techniques

The data collection techniques used in this study were observation methods, questionnaire methods, and documentation methods. To assess respondents' responses, the authors used the Likert scale. A good instrument must meet two important requirements, namely valid and reliable [18]. Data analysis techniques in this study use causality or influence relationships between research variables. This research uses a data analysis method using *WrapPLS* (*Partial Least Square*) software which is a structural equation analysis or *Structural Equation Model* (SEM). The steps of data analysis using PLS are:

2.3.1 Measurement Model (Outer Model)

A concept and research model cannot be tested in a relational and causal relationship prediction model if it has not passed the verification stage in the measurement model. In this model it uses validity tests and reality tests. The tests carried out on this outer model are as follows:

Convergent Validity The value of Convergent Validity is the value of the loading factor in the latent variable with its indicators. Expected value > 0.6

Discriminant Validity This value is a Cross Loading value, a useful factor to find out whether the construct has an adequate discriminant, namely by comparing the loading value on the intended construct must be more powerful than the loading value with other constructs.

Composite Reliability Data that has a composite reliability of > 0.7 means it has high reliability.

Average Variance Extracted (AVE) The expected AVE value > 0.5 .

Cronbach Alpha. The reliability test is reinforced with the Cronbach Alpha whose expected value > 0.7 for all constructs.

2.3.2 Structural Model (Inner Model)

Structural model (Inner Model) is a structural model to predict causality relationships between latent variables. After the estimated model meets the criteria of the Outer Model, the next is the structural model testing (Inner model). The evaluation of the structural measurement model (Inner Model) is determined based on the R-square value or coefficient of determination of the latent variable

R-square R-square is a measure of the proportion of variation in the value of an affected variable (endogenous) and can be explained by the variable that affects it (exogenous). According to [19] this is useful for predicting whether a model is good or bad.

Hypothesis testing, namely direct effect (direct effect) The purpose of direct effect analysis (direct influence) is useful to test the hypothesis of the direct influence of a variable that affects (exogenous) on the variable affected (endogenous).

Probability value/significance (P-Value): - If the value of P-Values < 0.05, then it is significant. - If the P-Values value > 0.05, then it is not significant.

The influence of interaction variables. Aims to measure how the interaction variable with other variables (moderation variables)

3 Results and discussion

3.1. Measurement Model (Outer Model)

This study uses questionnaires as a research data collection technique and to evaluate the validity of each statement item compiled in the questionnaire, this study uses data processing techniques with Partial Least Square (PLS) based methods to evaluate the reliability of variable constructs in the analysis model.

Figure 1 PLS Model Outer Path Diagram

There are three criteria for using data analysis techniques with SmartPLS to assess the outer model, namely convergent validity, discriminant validity, and reliability

3.2. Convergent Validity (Validitas Konvergen)

The first analysis is convergent validity analysis indicated by the outer loadings/loadings factor value. Loadings factor is a value that shows the correlation and measurement between indicators and latent variables. The loadings factor value is valid if it is greater than 0.6.

Table 1 Outer Loading Value

	Organizational Culture (BO)	Work Discipline (DS)	Leadership Style (GK)	Job Satisfaction (KK)	Information
B01	0.695				Valid
B02	0.774				Valid
B03	0.771				Valid
B04	0.635				Valid
B05	0.652				Valid
B06	0.695				Valid
B07	0.749				Valid
DS8		0.126			Invalid
DS1		0.799			Valid
DS2		0.762			Valid
DS3		0.783			Valid
DS4		0.800			Valid
DS5		0.783			Valid
DS6		0.818			Valid
DS7		0.870			Valid
GK1			0.744		Valid
GK2			0.734		Valid
GK3			0.817		Valid
GK4			0.808		Valid
GK5			0.784		Valid
GK6			0.746		Valid
KK1				0.724	Valid
KK2				0.800	Valid
KK3				0.730	Valid
KK4				0.761	Valid
KK5				0.817	Valid

Based on table 1. Found 1 (one) indicator that does not meet the criteria. The indicator is DS8. Then to correct these indicators, it is necessary to exclude and not include invalid indicators in the next test with the aim of increasing the measurement score of each statement model and a value of >0.6 .

Table 2 Outer Loading Value (Modified)

	Organizational Culture (BO)	Work Discipline (DS)	Leadership Style (GK)	Job Satisfaction (KK)	Information
B01	0.695				Valid
B02	0.774				Valid
B03	0.771				Valid

BO4	0.635				Valid
BO5	0.652				Valid
BO6	0.695				Valid
BO7	0.749				Valid
DS1		0.799			Valid
DS2		0.762			Valid
DS3		0.783			Valid
DS4		0.800			Valid
DS5		0.783			Valid
DS6		0.818			Valid
DS7		0.870			Valid
GK1			0.744		Valid
GK2			0.734		Valid
GK3			0.817		Valid
GK4			0.808		Valid
GK5			0.784		Valid
GK6			0.746		Valid
KK1				0.724	Valid
KK2				0.800	Valid
KK3				0.730	Valid
KK4				0.761	Valid
KK5				0.817	Valid

Based on table 2. through measurement (Outer loading) states that all variables and indicators meet the criteria so that they are declared valid.

3.3. Discriminant Validity

This value is a Cross Loading value, a useful factor to find out whether the construct has adequate discrimination, namely by comparing the loading value on the intended construct must be more powerful than the loading value with other constructs.

Table 3 Cross Loading Value

	Organizational Culture (BO)	Leadership Style (GK)	Work Discipline (DS)	Job Satisfaction (KK)
BO1	0.695	-0.222	-0.246	0.259
BO2	0.774	-0.047	-0.143	0.287
BO3	0.771	-0.215	-0.220	0.272
BO4	0.635	-0.019	-0.059	0.181
BO5	0.652	-0.024	-0.065	0.216
BO6	0.695	-0.027	-0.092	0.334
BO7	0.749	-0.038	-0.074	0.266

GK1	-0.188	0.744	0.516	0.024
GK2	-0.142	0.734	0.414	-0.037
GK3	-0.046	0.817	0.586	0.015
GK4	-0.055	0.808	0.521	0.040
GK5	-0.051	0.784	0.525	0.014
GK6	-0.136	0.746	0.777	-0.153
DS1	-0.078	0.640	0.799	0.030
DS2	-0.221	0.523	0.762	-0.080
DS3	-0.224	0.619	0.783	-0.038
DS4	-0.107	0.564	0.800	-0.040
DS5	-0.162	0.549	0.783	-0.039
DS6	-0.186	0.673	0.818	-0.055
DS7	-0.125	0.622	0.870	-0.032
KK1	0.279	0.160	0.054	0.724
KK2	0.268	-0.069	-0.020	0.800
KK3	0.291	-0.072	-0.079	0.730
KK4	0.279	-0.079	-0.080	0.761
KK5	0.309	-0.066	-0.031	0.817

From the results of cross loadings in table 3. indicates that the correlation value of the construct with its indicator is greater than the correlation value with other constructs. So that all constructs or variables already have good discriminant validity.

3.4. Cronbach's Alpha (CA), Composite Reliability (CR) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

The next analysis is a reliability test carried out to find out related to the consistency and regularity of the measurement results of an instrument. Reliability is determined based on Cronbach's Alpha, Composite Reliability, and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values. The construct is considered reliable if the composite reliability value is greater than 0.7 while some limitations regarding the Cronbach alpha score are greater than 0.6. Another way to assess discriminant validity other than the cross loading value is to look at the average extracted (AVE) value. A good model is required if the AVE of each construct is greater than 0.50.

Table 4 Cronbach's Alpha (CA), Composite Reliability (CR) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Average variance extracted (AVE)	Information
Organizational Culture (BO)	0.839	0.848	0.507	Reliable
Work Discipline (DS)	0.873	0.911	0.566	Reliable
Leadership Style (GK)	0.867	0.884	0.597	Reliable
Job Satisfaction (KK)	0.825	0.826	0.589	Reliable

From the results of table 4. It can be seen that all variables are in accordance with the criteria so that the variable is reliable.

3.5. Structural Model (Inner Model)

The next test is the inner model (testing on structural models). Testing of structural models is carried out by looking at the R-square value which is a goodness fit test of the model.

Figure 2 Output from PLS- Bootstrapping

3.6. Coefficient of Determination / R-Square / R2

In assessing structural models begins by looking at R2 for each dependent latent variable. Here is the R2 estimate:

Table 5 R-Square (R2)

	R-square	R-square adjusted
Work Discipline (DS)	0.571	0.565
Job Satisfaction (KK)	0.140	0.120

From the results of the R-square in table 5. It can be explained that the work discipline variable (DK) has an R-square value of 0.571. This shows that organizational culture (BO) and leadership style (GK) variables influence work discipline variables (DK) by 57% and 43% are influenced by other variables outside the variables studied.

While the job satisfaction variable (KK) has a value of 0.140. This value shows that the variables of organizational culture (BO), leadership style (GK) and work discipline (DK) have an influence on the variable of job satisfaction (KK) by 14% and 86% are influenced by other variables outside the variables studied.

3.7. Hypothesis Testing (Direct Effect)

Test the significance contained in the output of path coefficients after bootstrapping. This is done to strengthen the relationship between variables in each hypothesis. The significance test in this study uses a t-value of 1.697 where the relationship between variables can be said to be significant if the results of t-statistics > t-value (Widarjono2015) and Original sample to see the magnitude of influence.

Table 6 shows that the relationship between Organizational Culture (BO) and Work Discipline (DK) is insignificant and insignificant with T-statistics of 1.611 < 1.697 and p-values of 0.017 > 0.05. The original sample estimate value is

negative at -0.098 which indicates that the direction of the relationship between Organizational Culture (BO) and Work Discipline (DK) is negative.

Table 6 Path Coefficient

	Original sample (O)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Conclusion
Organizational Culture (BO) -> Work Discipline (DS)	-0.098	1.611	0.107	No Effect
Organizational Culture (BO) -> Job Satisfaction (KK)	0.379	5.111	0.000	Positive Influence
Work Discipline (DS) -> Job Satisfaction (KK)	0.040	0.285	0.776	No Effect
Leadership Style (GK) -> Work Discipline (DS)	0.737	22.066	0.000	Positive Influence
Leadership Style (GK) -> Job Satisfaction (KK)	-0.013	0.095	0.924	No Effect

The relationship between Organizational Culture (BO) and Job Satisfaction (KK) is significant with T-statistics of 5.111 > 1.697 and p-value 0.000 < 0.05. The original sample estimate value is positive at -0.379 which shows that the direction of the relationship between Organizational Culture (BO) and Job Satisfaction (KK) is positive.

The relationship between Work Discipline (DK) and Job Satisfaction (KK) is insignificant and insignificant with T-statistics of 0.285 < 1.697 and p-value 0.776 > 0.05. The original sample estimate value is positive at 0.040 which shows that the direction of the relationship between Work Discipline (DK) and Job Satisfaction (KK) is positive.

The relationship between Leadership Style (GK) and Work Discipline (DK) is influential and significant with T-statistics of 22.066 > 1.697 and p-value 0.000 < 0.05. The original sample estimate value is positive at 0.737 which shows that the direction of the relationship between Leadership Style (GK) and Work Discipline (DK) is positive.

The relationship between Leadership Style (GK) and Job Satisfaction (KK) is insignificant and insignificant with T-statistics of 0.095 < 1.697 and p-value 0.924 > 0.05. The original sample estimate value is negative at -0.013 which indicates that the direction of the relationship between Leadership Style (GK) and Work Discipline (DK) is negative.

3.8. Hypothesis Testing (Indirect Effect)

The output estimation results for indirect influence testing of structural models can be seen in the following table:

Table 7 Total Indirect Effect

	Original sample (O)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Conclusion
Leadership Style (GK) -> Work Discipline (DS) -> Job Satisfaction (KK)	0.029	0.282	0.778	No Effect
Organizational Culture (BO) -> Work Discipline (DS) -> Job Satisfaction (KK)	-0.004	0.233	0.815	No Effect

Based on the results in Table 7. obtained the results of the indirect influence of Organizational Culture (BO) on Job Satisfaction through Work Discipline with a path coefficient value of positive 0.029 and (P-Values = 0.778 > 0.05) means that there is no influence and insignificant between Organizational Culture (BO) on Job Satisfaction through Work Discipline (DK) of PT HKI Jakarta Employees.

And the results in Table 7. obtained the results of the indirect influence of Leadership Style (GK) on Job Satisfaction (KK) through Work Discipline (DK) with a path coefficient value of negative -0.004 and (P-Values = 0.815 > 0.05) means that

there is no influence and insignificant between Organizational Culture (BO) on Job Satisfaction through Work Discipline (DK) of PT HKI Jakarta Employees.

3.9. The Relationship between Organizational Culture (BO) and Work Discipline (DK)

According to (Sutrisno, 2018) Organizational culture is a strong determinant of beliefs, attitudes and behaviors of people within the organization, and its influence can be measured through how people or employees can be motivated and eager to respond to their cultural environment. Understanding and managing effective organizational culture can play a role in improving work discipline among organizational members, creating a productive work atmosphere, and supporting the achievement of common goals. The results of this study show that there is no influence on the relationship between organizational culture and work discipline of PT HKI Jakarta employees. So it can be concluded that organizational culture cannot affect the level of discipline of PT HKI Jakarta employees.

3.10. The Relationship between Organizational Culture (BO) and Job Satisfaction (KK)

The influence of organizational culture on employee job satisfaction can be explained as the interrelationship of elements that make up the work environment. A positive organizational culture, with values such as cooperation, innovation, and employee empowerment, can increase job satisfaction. Employees who feel connected to these values tend to be more motivated, valued, and have a sense of ownership of their work. The results of this study show that organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on the job satisfaction of PT HKI employees, meaning that P HKI is able to form a positive organizational culture that can feel a positive impact on employee job satisfaction, creating a productive and competitive work environment.

3.11. The Relationship between Work Discipline (DK) and Job Satisfaction (KK)

Good work discipline can contribute positively to employee job satisfaction. When work rules and norms are applied consistently and fairly, employees tend to feel safe and valued. Good discipline can also create an orderly work environment, minimize conflict, and increase productivity. However, the results of this study show that work discipline does not have a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of PT HKI Jakarta employees. While employees may abide by company rules and regulations, it doesn't automatically create satisfaction. Factors such as a less supportive work environment, lack of development opportunities, or lack of transparency in organizational communication can also affect job satisfaction.

3.12. The Relationship between Leadership Style (GK) and Work Discipline (DK)

Leaders who have a motivating and supportive leadership style can shape an environment where work discipline is considered an integral part of productivity and mutual success. The results of this study state that leadership style has a positive and significant influence on work discipline. Effective leadership, which includes elements such as example, support, and clear communication, can have a positive impact on employee discipline. Leaders who are able to provide clear direction and set an example in complying with company rules and norms can inspire employees to follow that example.

3.13. The Relationship between Leadership Style (GK) and Job Satisfaction (KK)

A leadership style that supports, encourages and focuses on employee development can increase job satisfaction. Leaders who are able to provide clear direction, listen to employee input, and reward their contributions tend to create a positive work environment. In this study shows the results that leadership style does not have a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction of PT HKI Jakarta employees. Although leaders may adopt a variety of leadership styles, such as democratic, authoritarian, or laissez-faire, there is no clear correlation with employee job satisfaction levels.

3.14. The Relationship of Organizational Culture (BO) to Job Satisfaction through Work Discipline (DK)

An organizational culture that is supportive, inclusive, and assigns value to employee contributions can form the foundation for a high level of work discipline. An organizational culture that encourages clear rules, norms, and values can motivate employees to abide by company rules, creating consistent work discipline. Good work discipline, in this case, can be a link that directs the positive influence of organizational culture on employee job satisfaction levels. However, this study shows that organizational culture does not have a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction through work discipline as an intervening variable.

3.15. The Relationship of Leadership Style to Job Satisfaction through Work Discipline

A leadership style that motivates, supports, and provides clear direction can improve work discipline, and through that work discipline, employees become more satisfied with their work. By understanding these relationships, companies can develop more effective leadership strategies to improve job satisfaction and overall employee performance. However, this study shows that leadership style does not have a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction through work discipline as an intervening variable.

4 Conclusion

Although work discipline and leadership style do not have a significant direct influence on job satisfaction, there is a positive direct influence between organizational culture and job satisfaction. Leadership style also has a direct positive influence on work discipline. This understanding can be the basis for the development of more effective management and leadership strategies at PT HKI Jakarta, with a particular focus on positive organizational culture and motivating leadership styles.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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